

Experimental design: Field Collections		PROJECT CODE (PC) PEMC			EXPERIMENT NO (EN):			SERIAL NO (SEN):															
		ASSAY NO (AYN):		FORM TYPE (FT): ED1		SITE (SI): ILUMA-CWMA																	
Form Row (FR)	Date of Collection (DT)	COLLECTION ATTRIBUTES											Valid Collection (VC): 1=yes/wet, 2=not carried out/totally failed 3=invalid/questionable	Destination Serial No. (DSEN)	Notes								
		GENERIC						EXPERIMENT SPECIFIC															
		Enumeration area (EA)	Cluster/Camp (CR)	Compound or Plot (CP)	Household (HH)	Structure/habitat ID (SID)	Method (ME)	Indoor/Outdoor (IN) (1 = in, 2 = out)	Habitat type (HT)	Start Time (STI)	Finish Time (FTI)	Holding Period (HP)				Round (RND)	Block (BLK)	House/Hut (SHH)	Station (STN)	Volunteer initials (VI)	Treatment (TR)	Experimental Day (DY)	Other (OTH)
		MARK X FOR ALL VARIABLES WHICH MUST BE RECORDED																					
A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	V	W	X	
01							3	2		19	07												
02							3	2		19	07												
03							3	2		19	07												
04							3	2		19	07												
05							19	2		19	20												
06							19	2		20	21												
07							19	2		21	22												
08							19	2		22	23												
09							19	2		23	00												
10							19	2		00	06												
11							3	2		19	07												
12							3	2		19	07												
13							3	2		19	07												
14							3	2		19	07												
15							19	2		19	20												
16							19	2		20	21												
17							19	2		21	22												
18							19	2		22	23												
19							19	2		23	00												
20							19	2		00	06												
EXPERIMENT SUPERVISORS INITIALS (ESI):											AND SIGNATURE:												
RESPONSIBLE SCIENTISTS INITIALS (RSI):											AND SIGNATURE:												

Method (ME): 01 = HLC; 02 = ITT; 03 = CDC LT; 04 = Resting box; 05 = Aspirator resting sites; 06 = Floor; 07 = Entry window; 08 = Entry eave; 09 = Entry; 10 = Exit window; 11 = Exit eave; 12 = Exit; 13 = PSC; 14 = Dip; 15 = Substrate; 16 = Emergence trap; 17 = Ovitrap; 18= Back pack; 19 = netting interception screen

Habitat type (HT): LARVAL HABITATS: 01 = Small puddles tracks and depressions; 02 = Swampy areas seepages and springs; 03 = Flowing stream bed; 04 = Flooded valley; 05 = Pond or water hole; 06 = Artificial drain or ditch; 07 = Wells and other human-made holes; 08 = Water storage & other artificial containers; 09 = Rice paddy; 10 = Ridge and furrow agriculture (matuta); 11 = Other agriculture; 12 = Others (describe):

ADULT HABITATS: 21 = In camp; 22 = Beside tent; 23 = Open natural glade; 24 = Open natural field; 25 = Woodland; 26 = Forest